

Methylenation Studies of Desoxybenzoins : Characterisation of Minor Products and Debenzylation of Benzyloxyisoflavanones

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The minor products in the reaction of 2-hydroxy-4-benzyloxydesoxybenzoins and methylene iodide are found to be corresponding enol-methylene ethers and 3-iodomethyl isoflavanones as shown by spectral studies. The latter compounds also form from the corresponding isoflavanones by reaction with methylene iodide under the same reaction conditions.

The best condition for debenzylation of benzyloxyisoflavanones is to heat with HCl : HOAc (1 : 2) at 60° for 10 min and for selective debenzylation in 5-position only for 2 min.

A reinvestigation of the synthesis of benzyloxyisoflavanones to afford hydroxyisoflavanones by methylene iodide method¹ has led to isolation and characterisation of minor products as presented below.

The crude product from reaction of 2-hydroxy-4-benzyloxy-phenyl benzyl ketone with methylene iodide¹ on careful chromatography over basic alumina gave two compounds 'A' and 'B' in addition to some impure fractions. Compound 'B' was identified as 7-benzyloxy isoflavanone(I)¹. Compound 'A' did not give any colour with ethanolic ferric chloride showing that ortho hydroxy group in phenyl benzyl ketone had been involved in the reaction. It was found to contain iodine, an inference substantiated by the loss of 128 mass units (mu) equal to HI in the mass spectrum. NMR revealed the presence of iodomethyl group at δ 3.65 which appeared as an AB quartet (J 9 Hz) showing its presence on an asymmetric carbon atom, a quartet at δ 4.9 (J 9 Hz) and integrating for 2H showed the presence of -O-CH₂-C* (C* being the asymmetric carbon) in addition to

other protons due to rings A and C and the benzyloxy group at position 7. Compound 'A' was thus assigned the structure 7-benzyloxy-3-iodomethyl isoflavanone (II). This could form by nucleophilic substitution involving the carbanion, derived from product B, and methylene iodide. To confirm this view, 7-benzyloxy isoflavanone (I) was refluxed with methylene iodide under conditions of the above experiment, when the same compound 'A' was formed.

Various fragments in the mass spectra are rationalised for structure (II) as shown in scheme-I.

A parallel set of experiments with 2-hydroxy-4,6-dibenzyloxy phenyl benzyl ketone gave three compounds C, D and E. Compound E, m.p. 180-81°, was identified as 5,7-dibenzyloxyisoflavanone from its spectral data and comparison with an authentic sample¹. Compound D, m.p. 166-67° was assigned the structure, 5,7-dibenzyloxy-3-iodomethyl isoflavanone (V) on the basis of spectral data. Mass spectral fragmentation was similar to the one observed for structure II (Scheme I) except for certain subtle differences. This structure V was finally confirmed by converting 5,7-dibenzyloxyisoflavanone into compound D by reaction with methylene iodide under the conditions described in a similar case.

Compound C, m.p. 124-26°, gave negative ferric reaction but a positive gallic acid-sulphuric acid test indicating a methylene dioxy group in the molecule. The presence of a methylene dioxy group was confirmed by an absorption at δ 5.3 in NMR. It showed the molecular ion peak at m/e 436. IR showed the absence of carbonyl frequency which led to the conclusion that the reaction with methylene iodide had involved the *o*-hydroxyl and enol form of phenyl benzyl ketone to yield the compound C having structure (III). This structure is supported by its NMR spectrum.

Debenzylation Experiments :

Debenzylation of benzyloxyisoflavanones with hydrochloric acid-acetic acid mixture has been found to be complicated because of the instability of isoflavanone nucleus. Best results were obtained by using hydrochloric acid-acetic acid mixture in the ratio of (1:2) at 60° for 8-10 minutes. However, partial debenzylaton of 5,7-dibenzyloxyisoflavanone could be accomplished in two minutes to get 7-benzyloxy-5-hydroxyisoflavanone.

Attempts at the synthesis of homoferreirin² by debenzylation of 5,7-dibenzyloxy-2', 4'-dimethoxyisoflavanone¹ by the above method were unsuccessful. This seems to be due to the additional complication arising from demethylation occurring at 2' position, which would account for the extremely complex nature of the reaction mixture.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. UV spectra were taken in methanol solution using a Hilger spectrophotometer. Infrared spectra were taken on a Perkin Elmer Infracord 137. NMR spectra were taken on

60 MHz Varian and 100 MHz JEOL spectrometers using tetramethylsilane as internal standard. Gallic acid-sulphuric acid test was taken as positive when an emerald-green colour appeared on heating at 80-90°.

7-Benzyloxy-3-iodomethyl isoflavanone (A) :

A mixture of 2-hydroxy-4-benzyloxyphenyl benzyl ketone¹ (1.5 g), methylene iodide (1.5 ml), potassium carbonate (10.0 g) and acetone (150 ml) was refluxed for 150 hr. The solvent was distilled off, water added and alkaline solution extracted with ether. Ether residue was treated with water and steam distilled to remove excess methylene iodide. The aqueous solution was once again extracted with ether and ether residue dried in vacuum over P₂O₅. The crude product was column chromatographed over basic alumina (50.0 g) using petroleum ether, petroleum ether-benzene (3:1) mixtures as eluents and fractions (50 ml each) collected and studied in TLC. Homogenous fractions were mixed and subjected to crystallisation when the following products were isolated.

(i) 7-Benzyloxy-3-iodomethyl isoflavanone (A) (II) was obtained from petroleum ether-benzene eluates

(fractions 3 to 10) as colourless shining prisms (0.13 g), m. p. 167-68°, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 280, 315 nm (log ϵ 4.18 & 3.92 respectively); $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}(>\text{C}=\text{O})$ 1680 cm^{-1} ; M^+ 470 (Found; C, 58.12; H, 4.30. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_3\text{I}$ requires C, 58.09; H, 4.04%).

The same product was obtained when 7-benzyloxyisoflavanone (0.15 g) in acetone (30.0 ml), methylene iodide (0.15 ml) and potassium carbonate (2 g) was refluxed for 65 hr.

(ii) 7-Benzyloxyisoflavanone (B) (I) was obtained from petroleum ether-benzene (3:1) eluates (fractions 16 to 36) as colourless shining plates (0.3 g) (from benzene-petroleum ether) m.p. 130-31°. Lit¹, m.p. 130-31°. It gave identical values of UV, IR and NMR data as recorded in lit¹.

Methylenation products of 2-hydroxy-4,6-dibenzyloxy-phenyl benzylketone :

A solution of 2-hydroxy-4,6-dibenzyloxyphenyl benzyl ketone (2.0 g), methylene iodide (2.0 ml) in acetone (200 ml) was refluxed with potassium carbonate (20.0 g) for 150 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as described earlier. 5,7-Dibenzyloxyisoflavanone (E) separated on maceration of crude product with ether. It was filtered and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture as colourless needles (0.8 g), m.p. 180-81°; lit¹, m.p. 180-81°. It gave identical values of UV, IR and NMR data as recorded in lit¹.

4,6-Dibenzyloxy- α -2-methylenedioxy stilbene (III) :

The above ether residue was chromatographed over basic alumina using petroleum ether, benzene-petroleum ether (1:9) and benzene-petroleum ether (1:3) mixtures.

Petroleum ether eluates on concentration gave an impure product. The crude product was purified by preparative TLC using silica gel as adsorbent and benzene-ethyl acetate (9:1) mixture as solvent system. Bands at R_f 0.72 were cut and eluted with ethyl acetate which on concentration gave enol methylene ether (III) (15 mg), m.p. 124-26° (from benzene-petroleum ether) $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 300 nm, M^+ 436. It gave negative ferric reaction but positive gallic acid-sulphuric test for methylene dioxy group.

NMR (CDCl_3): δ 4.95 & 5.1 (2H each, s, -O-CH₂-Ph at C5 & C7) 5.3 (2H, s, -O-CH₂-O-), 6.15 (2H, m, H6 & H8); 6.9 (1H, s, =CH-C₆H₅) and between 7.2

and 7.6 (15H, m, 10 aromatic of -O-CH₂-C₆H₅ at C5 and C7 and 5 aromatic protons of =CH-C₆H₅).

5,7-Dibenzyloxy-3-iodomethyl isoflavanone (V):

Petroleum ether-benzene (9:1) eluates on concentration afforded an impure product. A major product having R_f 0.62 on silica gel and benzene-ethyl acetate (9:1) as solvent system was purified by preparative TLC. when 5,7-dibenzyloxy-3-iodomethyl isoflavanone (D) was obtained as colourless crystals (20 mg) m.p. 166-67° (from benzene-petroleum ether), $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 290 nm,

$\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}(>\text{C}=\text{O})$ 1670 cm^{-1} . It gave negative ferric and negative gallic acid-sulphuric acid tests.

M^+ 576 (2%), 448 (100%), 406 (26%), 332 (2%), 116(2%) and 115 (8%).

NMR (CDCl_3): δ 4.1 (2H, AB q, J 9Hz, -CH₂ at C-3); between 4.6 and 5.0 (6H, m, 2H, of -OCH₂-C* (C* being asymmetric carbon atom) and 4H of O-CH₂-C₆H₅ at C5 and C7 respectively; between 6.4 and 7.4 (17H, m, 15 aromatic protons of side phenyl and two -O-CH₂-C₆H₅ and 2H of H6 and H8).

7-Hydroxyisoflavanone :

7-Benzyloxyisoflavanone (30.0 mg) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (5.0 ml) by warming at 60° and conc. hydrochloric acid (2.5 ml) added dropwise. The mixture was shaken at the above temperature for 10 minutes, and worked up as usual. The product on crystallisation from aq. methanol gave 7-hydroxyisoflavanone as colourless crystals (8.0 mg), m.p. 173-5°,

lit³, m.p. 175°; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 275, 315 nm (log ϵ 5.17 & 3.99

respectively). $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}(>\text{C}=\text{O})$ 1670 cm^{-1} .

7-Benzyloxy-5-hydroxyisoflavanone :

5,7-Dibenzyloxyisoflavanone (50 mg) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (5.0 ml) at 60° and conc. hydrochloric acid (2.5 ml) added dropwise. A yellow colour appeared and after two minutes at this temperature a solid crystallised out. On usual working up and crystallisation of the residue from aq. methanol afforded 7-benzyloxy-5-hydroxyisoflavanone as colourless solid (20 mg), m.p. 134-35°. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 290 nm (log ϵ 3.99)

$\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}(>\text{C}=\text{O})$ 1645 cm^{-1} .

NMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 3.9 (1H, t, J 7Hz, H3); 4.65 (2H, d, J 7Hz, CH_2 at C2); 5.1 (2H, s, $-O-CH_2-C_6H_5$ at C7); 6.3 (2H, m, H6 & H8); between 7.28-7.9 (10H, m, 5H, of side phenyl ring and 5 aromatic protons of $-O-CH_2-C_6H_5$) and 12.8 (1H, s, chelated -OH at C5).

5,7-Dihydroxyisoflavanone :

5,7-Dibenzoyloxyisoflavanone (30 mg) or 7-benzoyloxy-5-hydroxyisoflavanone (20 mg) was treated with acetic acid (3.0 ml) and hydrochloric acid (2.5 ml) as described above. The product on crystallisation from aq.

methanol gave 5,7-dihydroxy-isoflavanone (2.0 mg), m.p. 166-65°. Lit⁴ m.p. 163-5°. λ_{max}^{MeOH} 290 nm (log ϵ 4.31); $\nu_{(>C=O)}$ $\overset{KBr}{max}$ 1645 cm^{-1} .

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